

Supplementary Information – Methodology of Evaluating the Activation Energy of Oxygen Reduction Reaction on Pt/C Electrode in High Temperature H_3PO_4

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Table of content

S1 Standard redox potentials for ORR considering the formation of H_2O in the liquid and gaseous state.....	2
S2 Activity coefficient of liquid state H_2O in H_3PO_4 at higher temperatures.....	2
S3 Tafel slope values for ORR on Pt in H_3PO_4 at high temperature; from the literature.....	2
S4 Oxidative part of the exchange current density.....	2
S5 Dissociative path of ORR.....	3
Literature.....	6

S1 Standard redox potentials for ORR (E_{ORR}°) considering the formation of H_2O in the liquid (l) and gaseous (g) state

$t / ^{\circ}\text{C}$	$E_{\text{ORR,l},T}^{\circ} / \text{V}$	$E_{\text{ORR,g},T}^{\circ} / \text{V}$
120	1.148	1.163
140	1.131	1.158
160	1.115	1.153
180	1.098	1.149

S2 Activity coefficient of liquid state H_2O in H_3PO_4 at higher temperatures

Another possibility of determining the $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O,l}}$ would be using **Eq. A1** based on the concentration of H_2O , $c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, and the activity coefficient of H_2O in H_3PO_4 at a given temperature, $\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, according to **Eq. A1**.

$$a_{\text{H}_2\text{O,l}} = \gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \frac{c_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{c_{\text{st.}}} \quad \text{Eq. A1}$$

However, activity coefficient data are not available in the literature and in the context of a strong chemical interaction between H_2O and (poly)phosphoric acids involving complicated chemical equilibria, the application of the standard state based on an infinitely diluted solution of H_2O in H_3PO_4 seems obscure.

S3 Tafel slope values for ORR on Pt in H_3PO_4 at high temperature; from the literature

- [1] 164 mV dec^{-1} @ 136 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 85 wt. % H_3PO_4
- [2] 126 mV dec^{-1} @ 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 103 wt. % H_3PO_4
- [3] 125 mV dec^{-1} @ 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 98 wt. % H_3PO_4
- [4] 100 mV dec^{-1} @ 160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 99 wt. % H_3PO_4
- [5] 120 mV dec^{-1} @ 175 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 90 wt. % H_3PO_4

S4 Oxidative part of the exchange current density

Analogously to **Eq. 26-27**, the of the partial oxidation current density j_{ox} , i.e. the first term on the right side of **Eq. 25** can be expressed as **Eq. S2**.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{ox}} =$$

$$4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} \frac{a_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^3 c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^3} e^{\frac{3F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5 c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4 c_{\text{st}}^* + (E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'}) \right)}{RT}} \left(1 - \beta \right)^F \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5 c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4 c_{\text{st}}^* + (E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S2}$$

After rearrangement, the **Eq. S3** is obtained.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^3 c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^3} e^{-\frac{3}{4} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4}} e^{\frac{3F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'})}{RT}} e^{-\frac{(1-\beta)}{4} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{-3+3+1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{3}{4}+\frac{1}{4}-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{2-\frac{3}{2}-\frac{1}{2}+\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\ominus} c_{\text{st}}^{3-\frac{15}{4}-\frac{5}{4}+\frac{5\beta}{4}} e^{\frac{3F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'})}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{as}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{1-\frac{\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\ominus} c_{\text{st}}^{-2+\frac{5\beta}{4}} \left\{ e^{\frac{3F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_3^{\circ'}) + (1-\beta)F(E_{\text{ORR}}^{\circ'} - E_2^{\circ'})}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. S3}$$

S5 Dissociative path of ORR

When the **dissociative path** of the ORR is considered to take place, the overall reaction is:

The dissociative adsorption of O_2 leads to two O^* adsorbed on the Pt surface (**Eq. S4**).

Subsequently, the two adsorbed O^* undergo one-electron reductions forming adsorbed OH^* in two parallel RDSs (**Eq. S6**). In other words, this RDS has to occur two times in the reaction sequence.

Consequently, each OH^* formed in one RDS undergoes one electron reduction connected with protonation, see **Eq. S7**.

The overall current density is proportional to the current density of the two RDS steps (**Eq. S6**), j_{RDS} , expressed by the kinetic equation (**Eq. S8**)

$$j = 2j_{\text{RDS}} = 4F\bar{k}_{\text{dis}} c_{\text{OH}^*} e^{\frac{(1-\beta)F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT}} - 4F\vec{k}_{\text{dis}} c_{\text{O}^*} c_{\text{H}^+} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S8}$$

where $E_4^{\circ'}$ is formal potential of the RDS, i.e. **Eq. S6**, c_{x^*} represent the surface concentrations of individual adsorbed species and the subscript "dis" in k_{dis} indicates the dissociative O_2 adsorption pathway. Assuming chemical equilibrium in step (**Eq. S5**) preceding RDS, the equilibrium adsorption constant K_2 can be expressed as **Eq. S9**,

$$K_2 = \frac{a_{\text{O}^*}^2}{a_{\text{O}_2} a_{\text{O}^{\ominus}}^2} = \frac{\gamma_{\text{O}^*}^2 c_{\text{O}^*}^2 c_{\text{st}}^*{}^2}{\gamma_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{O}_2} \gamma_{\text{O}^{\ominus}}^2 c_{\text{O}^{\ominus}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^*{}^2} \quad \text{Eq. S9}$$

and when considering activity coefficients $\gamma_x = 1$, $c_{O_2^*}$ can be obtained using **Eq. S10**,

$$K'_2 = \frac{c_{O_2^*}^2 c_{st.}}{c_{O_2} c_{\ominus}^2}$$

$$c_{O_2^*} = \sqrt{\frac{K'_2 c_{O_2} c_{\ominus}^2}{c_{st.}}} \quad \text{Eq. S10}$$

where K'_2 is dimensionless apparent equilibrium constant. Analogously, the derivation of the c_{OOH^*} is based on assuming pseudo-equilibrium in the steps after RDS, i.e. **Eq. S7** by means of Nernst equation (**Eq. S11**).

$$E_5 = E_5^\circ - \frac{RT}{F} \ln \left(\frac{a_{H_2O,1} a_{\ominus}}{a_{H^+} a_{OH^*}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. S11}$$

Rearrangement provides the desired result **Eq. S12**. The standard state used for the adsorbed species is based on recommendations provided in [6]).

$$E_5 = E_5^\circ - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O} \cdot \frac{c_{\ominus}}{c_{st.}}}{\frac{c_{H^+}}{c_{st.}} \cdot \frac{c_{OH^*}}{c_{st.}}} \right) - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{\gamma_{H_2O,1} \gamma_{\ominus}}{\gamma_{H^+} \gamma_{OH^*}} \right)$$

$$E_5 = E_5^{\circ'} - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{x_{H_2O} \cdot \frac{c_{\ominus}}{c_{st.}}}{\frac{c_{H^+}}{c_{st.}} \cdot \frac{c_{OH^*}}{c_{st.}}} \right)$$

$$c_{OH^*} = \frac{x_{H_2O} c_{st.} c_{\ominus}}{c_{H^+}} e^{\frac{F(E_5 - E_5^{\circ'})}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S12}$$

After substituting the relations **Eq. S10** and **Eq. S12** into **Eq. S8**, the overall kinetic equation **Eq. S13** of the reaction **Eq. S4** is obtained.

$$j = 4F \bar{k}_{dis} \frac{x_{H_2O} c_{st.} c_{\ominus}}{c_{H^+}} e^{\frac{F(E_5 - E_5^{\circ'})}{RT}} \frac{(1-\beta) F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT} - 4F \vec{k}_{dis} \frac{c_{\ominus} c_{H^+} \sqrt{K'_1 c_{O_2}}}{\sqrt{c_{st.}}} e^{\frac{-\beta F(E - E_4^{\circ'})}{RT}}$$

Eq. S13

Since the reference potential in **Eq. S8** is formal potential $E_4^{\circ'}$ of reaction **Eq. S6**, it applies that $\bar{k}_{dis} = \vec{k}_{dis} = k_{dis}^\circ$. If it is moreover considered that step in **Eq. S6** represents RDS, it becomes obvious that this k_{dis}° value should be used in determining ΔG^\ddagger of the whole ORR process, i.e. the purpose of following derivation is to find dependence $k_{dis}^\circ = f(j_{ex}, c_{H^+}, c_{O_2}, x_{H_2O})$.

Having analytical expression for current density of the overall ORR (**Eq. S13**) allows to investigate also the corresponding exchange current density, j_{ex} . This can be done by setting the electrode potential E equal to E_{ORR} from Nernst equation for overall ORR process (**Eq. 10**).

Noting that this corresponds to state with $j = 0$ and consequently $j_{ex} = -j_{red} = j_{ox}$, where j_{ox} and j_{red} correspond to the first and second term on the right side of the **Eq. S13** and are called partial oxidation and partial reduction current density, respectively. For j_{red} , below **Eq. S14** can be obtained.

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{red}} = -4F\vec{k}_{\text{dis}} \frac{c_{\ominus} c_{\text{H}^+} \sqrt{K'_2 c_{\text{O}_2}}}{\sqrt{c_{\text{st}}}} e^{\frac{-\beta F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4} + (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4) \right)}{RT}} \quad \text{Eq. S14}$$

After rearrangement, the **Eq. S15** is obtained.

$$-j_{\text{ex}} = -4Fk_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1-\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^{\frac{\beta}{4}} c_{\ominus}^{\frac{-3}{2} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} c_{\text{st}}^{\frac{-3}{2} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} \left\{ \sqrt{K'_2} e^{\frac{-\beta F (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. S15} = \text{Eq. 31}$$

Analogously to the above treatment of j_{red} , the development of the partial oxidation current density j_{ox} , i.e. the first term on the right side of **Eq. S13** yields the very same dependence of j_{ex} on composition of the system. For j_{ox} , below **Eq. S16** can be obtained.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = j_{\text{ox}} = 4F\overleftarrow{k}_{\text{dis}} \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} c_{\text{st}} c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{H}^+}} e^{\frac{F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4} + (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5) \right)}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta) F \left(\frac{-RT}{4F} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4} + (E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4) \right)}{RT}}$$

Eq. S16

After rearrangement, the **Eq. S17** is obtained.

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} c_{\text{st}} c_{\ominus}}{c_{\text{H}^+}} e^{-\frac{1}{4} \ln \frac{x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4}} e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5)}{RT}} e^{-\frac{(1-\beta) x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^2 c_{\text{st}}^5}{4 c_{\text{O}_2} c_{\text{H}^+}^4}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta) F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{-1+1+1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1-\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1-\beta}{2} + \frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\ominus}^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{5}{4} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} c_{\text{st}}^{\frac{1}{4} - \frac{5}{4} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5)}{RT}} e^{\frac{(1-\beta) F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}}$$

$$j_{\text{ex}} = 4Fk_{\text{dis}}^{\circ} c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1-\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{4}} c_{\ominus}^{\frac{-3}{2} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} c_{\text{st}}^{\frac{-3}{2} + \frac{5\beta}{4}} \left\{ e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5) + (1-\beta) F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}} \right\} \quad \text{Eq. S17}$$

Considering that c_{\ominus} (in **Eq. S15** and **Eq. S17**) must be the same for both partial current density notations, j_{ox} and j_{red} differ (except for the sign) only by notation of constant terms. In particular, comparison of **Eq. S15** and **Eq. S17** yields **Eq. S18**, where the differences between E'_4 and E'_5 , K'_2 and E'_{ORR} stand out.

$$e^{\frac{F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_5) + F(E'_{\text{ORR}} - E'_4)}{RT}} = \sqrt{K'_2} \quad \text{Eq. S18}$$

After taking logarithm of **Eq. S18**, equality **Eq. S19** can be obtained,

$$-4FE'_{\text{ORR}} = -2FE'_4 - 2FE'_5 - RT \ln K'_2$$

$$-4FE^{\circ}_{\text{ORR}} - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{O}_2}} = -2FE^{\circ}_4 - 2FE^{\circ}_5 - RT \ln K_2 - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{O}^*}}{\gamma_{\text{O}_2} \gamma_{\ominus}^2} - RT \ln \frac{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O},l}^2 \gamma_{\ominus}^2}{\gamma_{\text{H}^+} \gamma_{\text{O}^*}^2}$$

$$\Delta G^{\circ}_{\text{ORR}} = \Delta G^{\circ}_2 + \Delta G^{\circ}_3 + \Delta G^{\circ}_1 \quad \text{Eq. S19}$$

which is consistent with Hess' law of the thermodynamic cycle supporting validity of the also supports validity of the (in **Eq. S6** 2 e⁻ are accepted, in **Eq. S7** 2 e⁻ are accepted, in the total reaction **Eq. S4** then 4 e⁻). By excluding the mostly unknown constant terms (curly brackets) in **Eq. S13** or **Eq. S17**, the desired relation between k°_{dis} and experimentally determined j_{ex}

value valid at given temperature is obtained, see **Eq. S20**. The only parameter, which is not easily available, is c_{\ominus} . It is important to mention that using **Eq. S20** only relative changes of the k°_{dis} could be obtained.

$$k^{\circ}_{\text{dis}} \propto \frac{j_{\text{ex}}}{c_{\text{H}^+}^{1-\beta} c_{\text{O}_2}^{\frac{1-\beta}{4}} x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\frac{\beta}{2}} c_{\ominus}} \quad \text{Eq. S20} = \text{Eq. 32}$$

However, if j_{ex} values are determined at various temperatures, variation of all parameters in in **Eq. S15** or **Eq. S17** must be considered (recall that the c_{H^+} was assumed constant due to lack of data). It is obvious that values such as c_{\oplus} , K'_2 and difference $E^{\circ'}_{\text{ORR}} - E^{\circ'}_4$ (or $E^{\circ'}_{\text{ORR}} - E^{\circ'}_5$) are not easy to obtain and one is left with simplifying assumption that they do not vary significantly with temperature. For K'_2 it can be assumed that its value should decrease with increasing temperature, while for c_{\oplus} its value should increase, so it is possible that these effects will be compensated. Due to lack of data, it was assumed that the molar ratio of H_2O in H_3PO_4 $x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ can be approximated the $a_{\text{H}_2\text{O},1}$ defined by **Eq. 13**.

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